

NEETE - Next Evolution Enhanced Text Editor

A Visual Text Editor

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Abstract

Computer programming is currently an exercise filled with difficulties in communication and understanding of the material. Most typical programming tools create little to no opportunity to communicate design and intentions to software practitioners who may encounter other people's creations. My view is that the lack of a clear and visible structure in complex systems exacerbates the problem.

I am of the belief that pictures and diagrams present an attractive option for improving communication. Therefore, a means of creating diagrammatic views of computer programs is presented in the form of Next Evolution Enhanced Text Editor (NEETE).

NEETE allows the creation of a higher level diagrammatic representation of the textual code, thus enabling the manipulation and exploration of the design in a multidimensional and hierarchical plane.

Keywords— programming cognitive overload, graphical overview, visual programming, code communication, intentions, code comprehension, program structure

1 Introduction

Difficulty in communicating ideas and cognitive overhead are realities in computer programming. Be it in learning to program[1] or in maintaining existing code[2]. The source of some of these issues may sit with the fact that most programs are not written to illustrate structure as intended by the programmer.

1.1 Structure

Whenever a programmer creates a software solution, they use a mental image of the structure which would be embedded in their mind[3]. In most environments, the discovery of this image by a third party can only come from learning the program code. More experienced programmers would use chunking based strategies to search through the code over time in a more or less trial and error approach intended to eventually uncover meaning[4]. For larger projects this can be a huge, if not impossible task.

Figure 1: Software Graphical Representations

It has been found that most programming time in institutions and organisations is spent reading and maintaining legacy code rather than writing code[5].

1.2 Intentions

The user of programming tools often has to go out of their way to communicate their intentions while putting together a solution[6].

Expression of these intentions can only really happen as a set of comments or as a separate document to describe the program. Figure 1 shows some popular software representations.

Mostly, unless a programmer is highly diligent, divergence of code and description is inevitable. This difference is often termed the Model-Code Gap[7].

1.3 Possibilities of Graphics

Imagery and graphics can assist in providing some relief from cognitive overload[8][9]. Imagery can be built to encourage the recipient to explore the information before them such that the structure, trends and intentions are immediately available.

Graphical approaches enable the depiction of different levels of detail at different scales[10]. This would be a similar mechanism to how a map can zoom out to view the entire planet at once, yet it can zoom in down to street level or even greater detail.

Another advantage of a diagrammatic approach is that it can be traversed in multiple axes. Text typically only moves in the direction of convention of the writing type; example, Latin based script would be left to right and then down, in something similar to a raster scan. Thus, diagrams afford the viewer random and immediate access to elements, so depiction is inherently multidimensional.

2 Existing Systems

Visual environments are generally found in two classes which are Visual Programming Languages (VPLs) and visualisations. The difference usually being that:

1. VPLs encompass the syntax and other programming structures completely in a graphical environment. This would mean the creation and editing of the program is done graphically, although sometimes, direct text editing may also be possible.
2. Visualisations create a graphical interpretation of an already existing computer program[11]. This may be done in order to enhance understanding or for the sake of analysis. Editing and execution are typically conventional processes with visualisations.

2.1 Visual Programming Languages

Some typical examples of VPLs are:

1. Quartz Composer from Apple[12], Blueprint Visual Scripting for Unreal Engine[13], Labview from National Instruments[14] and Node-Red originally from IBM[15]. These are the typical VPLs which are built on the notion of nodes and arcs. Nodes are operations and arcs represent data flow. These types of environments tend to be quite popular in multimedia and engineering applications.
2. Scratch [16] is a popular learning environment. The intention of scratch is to provide a fun and colourful programming environment so that younger learners can form an understanding of the principles of computing.
3. BlueJ [17] is built on an interpretation of Universal Modelling Language (UML) class diagrams. It gives a means of drawing object relational diagrams, then it generates the skeleton Java code underneath which can then be edited in the embedded editor and run.

2.2 Visualisations

Examples of visualisation systems are:

1. Designite [18] is a design quality assessment tool. It is built to provide a detailed metrics analysis. Above that it helps identify issues adding to design debt and assists in improving software design quality.

(a) “Quartz Composer”, Mindoftea, CC BY-SA 3.0
<https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/user:Mindoftea>

(b) “LabVIEW”, CC BY-SA 3.0
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/User:Smith_Pohl

Figure 2: Visual Programming Languages

2. SolidFX [19] is a reverse engineering environment built to assess the maintainability of C/C++ code bases. It was designed to support code parsing, fact extraction, metric computation, and interactive visual analysis of a given code base. Some of its listed abilities include: finding complexity hot-spots, assessment of modularity, assessing maintainability and tracking copy-and-paste patterns.

3 Theoretical Concepts

3.1 A View of Text - OHCO

The notion of structured text brings with it the idea of an Ordered Hierarchy of Content Objects (OHCO)[20].

3.1.1 Order

Order tends to be inherent in computer programs. Statements are executed one after the other and the order of this execution influences the desired outcome. Sometimes though, order exists unnecessarily. The nature of text is that it is serial and thus elements have to follow each other, even if this has no influence on the outcome. An example could be declarations of functions. Order is absolutely necessary in the program in some areas (either some small algorithmic implementation, or some necessary once off declaration e.g. a global variable).

Therefore it is a useful notion to apply order when necessary, but it would be good to reorder program elements when and where it could bring in other advantages such as logical grouping.

3.1.2 Hierarchy

Normally this would mean that we break down the text into constituents governed by markers. We then build the contained elements into some kind of hierarchical structure recursively. In the case of computer programs this could be the definition of a function, a class, loops, conditional structures, etc. These can form natural structures which most users can see. There may also be underlying subdivisions which are not visible, but are part of the programmers perception such as a section which calculates a known equation or subroutine.

Such arbitrary substructures may be useful for a programmer to treat in isolation. Other invisible hierarchical structures which are useful are conceptual groupings such as a group of functions which bear some similarity in application.

3.2 Human Memory Operation

3.2.1 Chunking

Chunking is a mechanism which allows the brain to manipulate large information sets in working memory[21]. This happens by amassing sets of possible scenarios over time and grouping them together.

This strategy is hypothesised to work in seasoned programmers. Over time they accumulate large groups of common design patterns which they seek out when deciphering new code[4].

3.2.2 Grouping

Grouping is a strategy used during information dissemination which can be likened to pre-chunking information. Grouping related bits of information provides a means for a recipient of information to better relate elements and thus speeding up the learning process[22].

4 Implementation

This project attempts to merge the propositions and theoretical background that have been stated. It is viewed as a way in which some of the difficulties of text based programming can be tamed such that we can have our cake and eat it too.

4.1 NEETE

NEETE, meaning Next Evolution Enhanced Text Editor presents a different way of viewing those same programs by creating an alternative view of the text. What this does is to enable a graphical approach to creating and editing text. Graphical here is capturing two senses of the word i.e.

1. Drawing pictures on a screen,
2. Mathematical nodes and arcs.

The entire proposition is carried by the two elements i.e. node and arc, and how these are creatively combined in a project.

4.2 Summary of Strategy

The approach here is to reduce chunking based strategies and mental imagery that are mentioned in Section 1.1. These strategies require time and experience and thus carry a high cognitive overhead. Instead, this work is promoting visible grouping and explicit structure i.e. visible imagery, similar to Section 3.2.2.

Using OHCO principles mentioned in Section 3.1, the practitioner can break text into logical snippets. These form content objects. These content objects are carried as codeboxes. Codeboxes can be ordered using arcs, priorities and positioning. These codeboxes can then be placed in containers to form hierarchies. The terms *codebox*, *container*, *node*, *arc* and *priority* will be given deeper treatment later in the section.

These nodes and arcs combine to form a visible image which would reduce the necessity of a mental image. This structure also forms a sense of a model, yet it is tightly intertwined with the content such that it greatly reduces model-code gap as stated in Section 1.2. A practical example to illustrate this approach is Figure 11 which is found in Section 5.3.

4.3 Design Considerations

The design basis for this project is 2 dimensional. 3 dimensional design presents difficulties with visual occlusion, which will detract from the main goal of clarity and communication.

4.3.1 Nested Containment

Representing text as OHCO is usually done using a node-link style tree structure as in Figure 3a. This conventional tree representation works by means of nodes and arcs with lower down nodes in the hierarchy branching off from the higher level node. Node-link representation is usually great at depicting hierarchy.

The main problem with a node-link representation is that it is not space efficient. Positioning of elements is usually fixed and thus does not communicate extra relational information well[23].

Nested containment as shown in Figure 3b is an alternative tree representation that has certain advantages for this application. Containment is space efficient and positioning tolerant. Visually this gives great advantages in terms of grouping and positioning elements to form logical relationships.

Figure 3: Tree Representations

4.3.2 Shape

The basic design element in this solution is a box container. Boxes are naturally space efficient because they fit well with each other and within each other without needlessly occupying extra space. Boxes are also well suited for computer screens which are mostly rectangular, thus allowing elements to fit optimally within the display as well.

A facility is also available to decorate the borders on nodes so that they depict different ideas. Some of this is illustrated in the differentiation of codeboxes vs. containers in the coming sections.

Positioning is liberal and sizing is free, this way the user can formulate a visual representation of the underlying solution which best suits their intentions.

4.4 Nodes

A node is the principle building block for NEETE. The same node is used in two scenarios:

1. To carry text (where it's termed a codebox),
2. To carry nodes (where it's termed a container).

The same one node does both jobs but in different scenarios. The determinant is whether or not it contains another node and this difference shows up during rendering.

Nodes also carry with them two other visible features, which are title and priority. A description field is included, but this is more or less a comment feature with no real consequence on operations.

4.4.1 Codebox - Head, Tail and Textbox

Figure 4: The Codebox

On the inside of a node there are three other important text fields, which are the head, tail and textbox. These are pertinent for the actual low level of operations and they form the basis of the text. Upon rendering a codebox, these elements are batched in the order: *head* then *textbox* then *tail*.

The head and tail are very important for containers because they allow an operator to be bound to the contained nodes.

The head and tail can also be useful in helping maintain codebox scope, because they allow mandatory fields to be taken out of the core code at hand and be maintained separately. An example could be a “for” statement where the head would contain

```
for(i = 0; i < 10; i++) {
```

and the tail may have “}” then the body is in the textbox. That way the programmer can focus their attention better on the body without being distracted by the syntax of the “for”.

The textbox is meant to carry small manageable snippets of code. This is where the bulk of the text is carried in the project. The size of this snippet is up to the discretion of the programmer. The idea here being that it must be a simple enough section to read through and understand in a short space of time.

4.4.2 Container

Containers behave mostly similarly to codeboxes. The difference is that the textbox in a container will contain a continuous strip of the text from the contained nodes. These will be attached tip to tail in their rendering order.

Containers may act as passive holders of nodes purely for logical grouping or they can apply an operator to those nodes that they contain. An example of such could be a “for” loop, a “while” operator or an “if” statement. This comes about because the head and tail give containers the ability to hold scope over the nodes that they contain.

4.5 Arcs

Figure 5: Nodes Joined by Arcs

The arc is present to allow a follow sequence to be determined and it outputs from the right of a node and inputs into the left of the follower.

4.6 Putting it Together

(a) Nodes of different priorities in a container

(b) Node colour codes

Figure 6: Priorities and Colour Codes

The relationship between codeboxes, containers and arcs then comes together during rendering. Here a few simple rules determine the outcome. Text in the output is sourced from the *heads*, *textboxes* and *tails*.

When the system renders a node, it begins with the head. Then depending on whether it's a codebox or a container it will render the textbox or the contained nodes recursively and lastly renders the tail.

The text rendering process starts at the first node. The first node is found at the highest level of nodes i.e. nodes which are not contained by any other nodes. Nodes at any equal level in a container are then ordered by priority, arcs or position.

Nodes may have 10 priorities as shown in Figure 6b, so this feature must be used sparingly. Priority 0 is the highest and 9 is the lowest. With nodes at the same level, the highest priority is rendered first and the lowest is rendered last. The priority is visible as a colour code on the frame of the node. Nodes which have the same priority, at the same level of a container are picked by the order of their positioning i.e. from top left to bottom right similar to a raster scan.

Using this simple set of rules, the system will stitch together all the text contained in the nodes and give out a rendered text file to be used as desired.

4.7 Focus and Ignore

4.7.1 Focus

This is a feature which allows the elements of a container to occupy the entire view, thus putting them in focus. It is useful whenever attention needs to be placed on a particular container.

Figure 7: Resized Containers and Focus

A situation though where “Focus” is imperative is a case where a container has been shrunk to a point where the nodes contained become hard to see or where NEETE has determined that they are too small to render. At that point, the inside of the container will have a hatched pattern as in Figure 7a. This pattern reminds the user that the node is a container and has elements which have become too small to see. In order to view details on such a container either it have to be expanded or it will need to be focused. When in focus mode, the top bar changes to highlight the name of the container as in Figure 7b.

This feature allows the user to drill deeper into detail where necessary and it allows control over the amount of attention needed in different scenarios.

4.7.2 Ignore

“Ignore” is a tick box that can be selected on any node, be it a container or a codebox. Once selected, the node will be struck out visually with an “X” as in Figure 8.

A node which is set to “Ignore” will have its contents ignored on the text output rendering. Therefore it serves the same purpose as commenting out lines of source code.

5 Usage Examples

As stated before, NEETE allows the manipulation of text in a graphical form and this gives the text “shape and form”. This strategy allows the viewing and editing of “closer to physical” objects with an

Figure 8: Node to Ignore

Figure 9: API for SMS

explicitly shown relationship. A number of real world applications have been built utilising NEETE's graphical system to illustrate its usefulness.

5.1 SMS API

A first example shown in Figure 9 shows an Application Programming Interface (API) created for an Short Messaging Service (SMS) server. The underlying language used is PHP Hypertext Processor (PHP) with a micro-framework called Fat Free Framework.

The view shown has the underlying text details hidden away and the elements making up the project are prominent. The relationships between these elements are illustrated by how they are contained and how they sit in the same container. The priorities of these nodes are colour coded. As mentioned before, the exact code underneath does not distract the overall flow and intention of the programmer's vision.

The code shown renders to ~800 lines of code. In a conventional text editor, that many lines would not be visible at once and the relationship between different sections of the code would not be easy to grasp, but as shown in the figure, NEETE creates such a possibility. The layout is apparent in a few glances on an average laptop monitor.

5.2 CNC Drill Controller

Figure 10 shows the design for control software for a Computer Numeric Control (CNC) drill. The code is written in Python and incorporates Gnome Tool Kit (GTK) for the user interface. The drill loads locations

Figure 10: CNC Control Software

(a) An HTML form example

(b) The real HTML page

Figure 11: HTML Form Example

stored in a Gerber file, but uses machine vision to verify these locations and to ensure precise drilling.

The image shows how the code has been split into separate classes and shows how the various callbacks and other pertinent methods come together to build the final solution.

5.3 HTML Form

Figure 11 shows a HyperText Markup Language (HTML) form built for a website.

The notable feature in this example is the way in which the NEE/TE form of the code has its elements similarly positioned to the corresponding output from the site.

This illustrates the versatility of a graphical system such as this.

As a contrast, the actual HTML rendered from the NEE/TE code is shown in Appendix A.

6 Conclusion

The lack of a visible and explicit structure has been highlighted as a possible problem area in the communication of intention in computer programs. This may also be a probable source of cognitive overload for

computer programmers.

NEETE is a structural and pictorial enhancement to conventional text representation. This means it is also applicable to multitudes of other scenarios where text is used, be it technical documentation design, legal document layout or even a movie script. This can happen since it gives a visual and diagrammatic approach to generic text editing. It does this in a way that hides away the underlying text and allows the user to move to a two dimensional graphical view that facilitates navigation and exploration.

When using this system, opening a codebox for editing would probably be akin to pulling out a lens or a microscope to view issues at greater detail. Closing off that detailed view allows the user to revert back to a zoomed out view where they can deal with the overall layout.

The ability to recursively contain nodes allows programmers to be infinitely creative about how different ideas and intent group together logically in a way which is easily visible and simpler for third parties to follow.

A HTML Form Code Listing

```
<form method="POST" action="notesubmit" id="note_form">
<div class="w3-card-4">
<div class="w3-container w3-green">
<h3>Note Details</h3>
</div>
<table style="width:100%">
<tr valign="top">
<td valign="top" width="50%">
<table style="width:80%">
<tr>
<td> <label for="notetype">Note type</label></td>
<td> <input type="text" id="notetype" name="notetype" value="{{@type}}" > </td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td><label for="note">Note</label></td>
<td><textarea id="note" name="note" rows="4" style="width:100%" style="font-size: 10pt">{{@note}}</textarea></td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td width="20%"> <label for="time">Event Time</label></td>
<td> <!--input type="text" id="time" name="alarmtime"-->
<input type="datetime-local" name="logtime" value="{{@logtime_corrected}}" > </td>
</tr>
</table>
</td>
<td valign="top" width="50%">
<table style="width:80%">
<tr>
<td> <label for="user">User</label></td>
<td> <input type="text" id="user" name="username" value="{{@username}}" disabled </td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td width="20%"> <label for="logtime">Logtime</label></td>
<td> <!--input type="text" id="time" name="alarmtime"-->
<input type="datetime-local" name="alarmtime" value="{{@alarmtime_corrected}}" disabled </td>
</tr>
</table>
</td>
</tr>
</table>
</div>
<input type="hidden" id="note_id" name="note_id" value="{{@note_id}}">
<br>
<br>
<div align="right"><button type="button" class="w3-btn w3-white w3-border w3-border-grey w3-round" style="width: 150px" onclick="doCancel();">Cancel</button> <
input type="submit" value="Submit"></div>
</form>
```

Acronyms

API Application Programming Interface. 8

CNC Computer Numeric Control. 9

GTK Gnome Tool Kit. 9

HTML HyperText Markup Language. 9, 10

IBM International Business Machines. 2

NEETE Next Evolution Enhanced Text Editor. 1, 4, 5, 7–10

OHCO Ordered Hierarchy of Content Objects. 3, 4

PHP PHP Hypertext Processor. 8

SMS Short Messaging Service. 8

UML Universal Modelling Language. 1, 2

VPL Visual Programming Language. 2

Data availability statement

Program code and some examples for this project are available on: <https://github.com/ashe-cuena/neete>

Compliance with Ethical Standards:

The author declares that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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